

FEATURES OF HEALTH STATUS AND ADAPTATION PERIOD IN LATE PRETERM INFANTS

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Abstract. *Currently, neonatologists worldwide pay special attention to the group of preterm infants due to the higher risk of morbidity and mortality. Objective of the study is to investigate the features of health status and the course of the adaptation period in late preterm infants. We examined 115 children, including a main group of 60 late preterm infants (children born between 34 0/7 and 36 6/7 weeks of gestation), a comparison group of 35 term infants with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), and a control group of 20 term, practically healthy newborns. The features of adaptation significantly complicated the course of the neonatal period and required transfer of late preterm infants to the care unit almost 30% more often. The number of bed-days in the hospital was significantly different from the hospitalization duration of term newborns and infants with IUGR. The most common reasons for hospitalization of late preterm infants were issues related to feeding, respiratory system disorders, and central nervous system damage (cerebral excitability of newborns, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy), which exceeded the frequency of similar disorders multiple times.*

Keywords: *late preterm, intrauterine growth restriction, newborn, morbidity, adaptation period.*

Currently, neonatologists worldwide pay special attention to preterm infants due to the higher risk of morbidity and mortality compared to term infants and a higher incidence of psychomotor development disorders. Late preterm infants are categorized as those born due to premature labor occurring between 34 weeks 0/7 and 36 weeks 6/7 days, or from 239 to 259 days from the first day of the last menstrual period [1,8,9].

In the international literature, late preterm infants have been defined for several decades by various terms: late preterm, slightly preterm, moderately preterm, minimally preterm, and weakly preterm. The term "preterm" was long the most common [1, 2, 4, 6]. However, the use of the term "near-term" often led to an underestimation of the risks of poor adaptation, morbidity, and mortality in preterm infants [1, 2, 7, 9].

The proportion of late preterm infants constitutes 4-15% of all births and 70-80% of preterm births [1, 2, 10].

Late preterm infants have a higher risk of developing diseases and conditions compared to preterm infants and often face adverse outcomes [5,6]; in an Austrian study from 2014, the morbidity rate for preterm newborns at 36 weeks was 24%, at 35 weeks it was 43%, and at 34 weeks it was 55% [8]; J.E. Williams and Y. Pugh reported that in 2018, the morbidity rate for infants with a gestational age (GA) of 34 weeks was 51% [12].

Neonatal mortality among late preterm newborns is significantly higher than among term infants [5, 7]. According to A.L. Jefferies et al., neonatal mortality among late preterm infants is 1.2% [9]. In the USA, the neonatal mortality rate among late preterm infants is 4.5 times higher than among term infants. The mortality rate remains high even at older ages [2, 4, 5]. Late preterm

infants are more likely to die within the first year of life [1, 5, 10]. The infant mortality rates among late preterm infants in the USA were three times higher than among preterm infants (7.7 and 2.5 per 1000 live births, respectively) [5].

A higher frequency of intrauterine growth restriction has been noted among late preterm infants. According to the Federal State Budgetary Institution "National Medical Research Center for Obstetrics, Gynecology and Perinatology named after V.I. Kulakov" of the Ministry of Health of Russia, it is 20% among preterm infants at a gestational age of 34 weeks, 20.1% at 35 weeks, and 12.9% at a gestational age of 36 weeks.

The overall incidence of intrauterine growth restriction in late preterm infants is 16% [9]. There is a trend towards an increase in neonatal disorders as gestational age decreases [8], and according to J.E. Williams and Y. Pugh, the morbidity in the late preterm group doubles with each gestational age less than 36 weeks [5].

Compared to preterm newborns, late preterm infants have a higher risk of developing conditions such as respiratory problems, intrauterine infections, thermoregulation disorders, apnea, nutrient absorption issues, thrombocytopenia, polycythemia, hyperbilirubinemia, hypoglycemia, and other metabolic disorders that have significant features during the early neonatal adaptation phase [1]. However, the issues related to the care of late preterm infants receive insufficient attention in domestic medical literature.

Objective of the study: To investigate the health status and adaptation period characteristics in late preterm infants.

Materials and methods: To achieve the objectives, 115 children were examined: the main group consisted of 60 late preterm infants (children born no earlier than 34 0/7 weeks and no later than 36 6/7 weeks of gestation), the comparison group included 35 term infants with intrauterine growth restriction, and the control group consisted of 20 term, practically healthy newborns.

Data collection was based on the results of clinical and laboratory examinations using a specially developed card with standard accounting forms. The source of information was a comprehensive clinical examination of the children included in the study: analysis of medical documents ("History of Newborn Development" (form No. 097/u); "Medical Record of Inpatient" (form No. 003/u)) and the results of the child's examination.

Statistical processing of the obtained data was performed using Statistica 6.0 software. The Student's t-test was used to assess the significance of differences between the mean values of the indicators.

Results: The analysis of the characteristics of the neonatal period showed that in the main group of 60 newborns, the average body weight was 2768.9±495.5 g, with a height of 50.15±3.32 cm (Table 1). When analyzing the gestational age at birth, it was found that 20% (12 children) were at 34 weeks of gestation, 16.7% (10 children) - at 35 weeks, 16.7% (10 children) - at 36 weeks of gestation, and 53.3% (32 children) - at 37 weeks of gestation.

Table 1

Characteristics of the early postnatal period of children in the studied groups

Characteristic	Main group n = 60	Comparison group n = 35	Control group, n = 20	P

Body weight (gr)	2492,6±58,9	2302,9±52,2	3340,6±67,4*	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ <0,05 P ₃ <0,05
Body length (cm)	46,0±0,6	45,2±0,5	52,8±0,7*	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ >0,05 P ₃ <0,05
Apgar score at 1 minute	6,88±0,95	6,26±0,56	8,06±0,27	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ >0,05 P ₃ <0,05
Apgar score at 5 minutes	8,17±0,8	8,03±0,71	8,96±0,49	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ >0,05 P ₃ >0,05
Primary resuscitation in the delivery room	6,7%	17,2%	-	P ₁ <0,001

Note - P₁ – the significance of differences between group 1 and group 2; P₂ – the significance of differences between group 1 and group 3; P₃ – the significance of differences between group 2 and group 3.

When analyzing the indicators of physical development of children in the main group at birth according to Fenton's tables, it was found that the percentage of children classified as "small for gestational age: <10th percentiles" was 6.7% for body weight and 6.7% for body length. The percentage of children "appropriate for gestational age: from 10th to 90th percentiles" was 78.3% for body weight and 66.7% for body length among newborns. The percentage of children diagnosed as "large for gestational age: over 90th percentiles" was 15.0% for body weight and 26.7% for body length.

Consequently, more than half of the children at birth had average physical development indicators for their gestational age. The second comparison group (newborns with intrauterine growth restriction, IUGR) showed no differences from the "late preterm" group in terms of body weight and height at birth, with an average weight of 2302.9±52.2 grams and an average height of 45.2±0.5 cm. Among them, 60% of the children had an asymmetric type of IUGR, while 40% had a symmetric type. 28.6% of the children fell below the 3rd percentile for body weight, while 71.4% of newborns were in the range from the 3rd to the 10th percentile. No children had body weights above the 10th percentile.

When assessing body length, it was found that 11.4% of children were below the 3rd percentile, 28.6% were from the 3rd to the 10th percentile, 37.1% were from the 10th to the 50th percentile, and 22.8% were from the 50th to the 90th percentile, with no newborns exceeding the 90th percentile for length.

The Apgar score for late preterm children at 1 minute averaged 6.88±0.95, with the majority of children (74.1%) being born with Apgar scores of 7-8 points. At the same time, an Apgar score of 0/3 was observed in 6.7% of children, and 30% of children were born with scores of 4/6; 63.3% of newborns received scores of 7/8 points.

At 5 minutes, the indicators normalized, and the average score was 8.17±0.8 points, with only 3.3% of children maintaining a low Apgar score of 4 points. By the fifth minute, 10% of

newborns were rated at 6 points, and 16.7% - at 7 points. The score normalized to 8 points for 58.3% of children, and to 9 points for 8.3%.

The Apgar score at 1 minute for children with IUGR was 6.26 ± 0.56 points and did not significantly differ from the study group (6.88 ± 0.95 points). At 5 minutes, the score was 8.03 ± 0.71 points, which did not significantly differ from the children in the study group but was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than that of the full-term children in the control group.

Every third "late preterm" child required resuscitation assistance in the delivery room (36.7%), with minimal interventions (tactile stimulation, supplemental oxygen) needed for 31.7% of children, while tracheal intubation, respiratory support, and full primary resuscitation were necessary for only 3 children (5%).

Children with IUGR required intensive therapy involving full resuscitation measures 2.5 times more often ($P < 0.05$) in 17.2% of cases than late preterm children (5.0%).

In analyzing the data from the early postnatal period of "late preterm" children, it was found that their body weight and length at birth were significantly lower than those of term-born children ($P < 0.05$), but did not differ from the physical development indicators of children in the second comparison group.

Thus, the impact of protein-energy deficiency during the intrauterine period, manifested as IUGR, on physical development indicators was comparable to the impact of premature cessation of intrauterine development.

The average Apgar score at one minute was 6.88 for "late preterm" children and 6.26 for children with IUGR, which did not significantly differ, while the need for full resuscitation interventions, including tracheal intubation and mechanical ventilation, was more frequently noted in newborns with IUGR.

Normalization of the Apgar score at the fifth minute, which showed no significant differences in all three groups, indicated sufficient adaptive capabilities of the body in "late preterm" infants. The further state of neonatal adaptation in "late preterm" infants was characterized by a cascade of adaptive process disturbances (Table 2).

Table 2

Characteristics of the early neonatal period in children in the study groups

Characteristic	Main group n = 60	Comparison group n = 35	Control group, n = 20	P
Breastfeeding	$30,0 \pm 6,2\%$	$62,9 \pm 6,6\%$ 22	$80,0 \pm 5,4\%$	$P_1 > 0,05$ $P_2 < 0,05$ $P_3 < 0,05$
Mixed feeding	$38,3 \pm 6,6\%$	$20,0 \pm 5,4\%$ 7	$15,0 \pm 4,8\%$ 3	$P_1 < 0,05$ $P_2 < 0,05$ $P_3 > 0,05$
Artificial feeding	$31,7 \pm 6,3\%$	$17,1 \pm 4,8\%$ 5	$5,0 \pm 3,0\%$ 1	$P_1 > 0,05$ $P_2 < 0,05$ $P_3 < 0,05$

Regurgitation	36,7±6,6%	20,0±5,4% 7	10,0±4,1% 2	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ <0,05 P ₃ <0,05
Skin marbling	43,3±6,7%	28,6±6,1% 10	15,0±4,8% 3	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ <0,05 P ₃ <0,05
Jaundice more than 4 st. according to Kramer	31,7±6,3%	14,3±4,8% 5	10,0±4,1% 2	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ <0,05 P ₃ <0,05
Pathological weight loss ≥10%	25,0±5,9%	11,4±4,3% 4	5,0±3,0% 1	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ <0,05 P ₃ <0,05
Transfer to the neonatal pathology department	43,3±6,7%	25,7±5,9%	-	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ <0,05
Duration of inpatient treatment, bed-days	14,29±2,91	9,73±1,19	-	P ₁ >0,05 P ₂ <0,05 P ₃ <0,05

Note - p₁ – significance of differences between groups 1 and 2; p₂ – significance of differences between groups 1 and 3; p₃ – significance of differences between groups 2 and 3.

Our studies showed that only one-third of "late preterm" infants were exclusively breastfed from birth - 30.0±6.2%, while 38.3±6.6% were on mixed feeding and 31.7±6.3% were on artificial feeding. Difficulties in organizing proper enteral nutrition were also associated with pathological weight loss, observed in a quarter of "late preterm" infants (25.0±5.9%).

Clinically significant regurgitation was noted in more than one-third of "late preterm" infants (36.7±6.6%), and vascular regulation disorders, manifested as mottled skin, were diagnosed in 43.3±6.7% of cases. Pathological hyperbilirubinemia with jaundice greater than grade 4 according to Kramer (bilirubin level in peripheral blood in the range of 200-250 μmol/L), due to the immaturity of liver enzymatic systems, was found in almost every third "late preterm" newborn (31.7±6.3%).

In light of the above circumstances, a significant portion of "late preterm" newborns (45.0±6.8%) required continued treatment at the next stage, with the duration of inpatient treatment averaging 14.29±2.91 days. A quarter of newborns with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) required hospitalization in the neonatal pathology department (26.92±0.26%) for an average of 3.72±1.19 days, while the remaining (28.1±1.26%) were discharged home in satisfactory condition on the 5th to 7th day of life.

Neonatal adaptation in late preterm infants also had its peculiarities. For instance, exclusive breastfeeding was significantly (p<0.05) less common among late preterm infants compared to the other two groups. "Late preterm" infants were more than twice as likely to be on mixed and artificial feeding compared to the comparison groups (p<0.05).

Conclusions: thus, the aforementioned peculiarities of adaptation significantly complicated the course of the neonatal period and required "late preterm" infants to be transferred to the care unit almost 30% more frequently. The number of inpatient bed-days significantly differed from the hospitalization duration of full-term newborns and infants with IUGR. The most common

reasons for hospitalization of "late preterm" infants were issues related to feeding, respiratory system disorders, and central nervous system damage (newborn excitability, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy), which were significantly more frequent than similar disorders.

REFERENCES

1. Belousova T.V., Andryushina I.V., Bykadorova O.L., Grinberg I.G., Gorbatykh T.A. Features of late preterm infants in the conditions of the regional perinatal center. *Sibirskiy nauchnyy meditsinskiy zhurnal = Siberian Scientific Medical Journal*. 2020; 40 (1): 124–130. doi 10.15372/SSMJ20200117
2. Bouchet N., Gayet-Ageron A., Lumbreras Areta M., Pfister R.E., Martinez de Tejada B. Avoiding late preterm deliveries to reduce neonatal complications: an 11-year cohort study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2018; 18(1): 17. DOI: 10.1186/s12884-017-1650-8
3. Correia C., Rocha G., Flor-de-Lima F., Guimarães H. Respiratory morbidity in late preterm infants. *Minerva Pediatr*. 2018; 70(4): 345–54. DOI: 10.23736/S0026-4946.16.04580-1
4. Jefferies A.L., Lyons E.R., Shah P.S., Shah V. Impact of late preterm birth on neonatal intensive care resources in a tertiary perinatal center. *Am. J. Perinatol*. 2013; 30(7): 573–8. DOI: 10.1055/s0032-1329685
5. Kiosov A.F. Late Preterm Infants: Epidemiological Aspects, Morbidity, and Approaches to Medical Management. *Doctor.Ru*. 2019; 9(164): 19–24. (in Russian) DOI: 10.31550/1727-2378-2019-164-9-19-24
6. Mally P.V., Hendricks-Muñoz K.D., Bailey S. Incidence and etiology of late preterm admissions to the neonatal intensive care unit and its associated respiratory morbidities when compared to term infants. *Am. J. Perinatol*. 2013; 30(5): 425–31. DOI: 10.1055/s-0032-1326989
7. Sofronova L.N., Fedorova L.A., Kyanksep A.N., Shevareva E.A., Yalfimova E.A. Pozdnie nedonoshennye — gruppа vysokogo riska rannikh i otdalennykh oslozhnenii. *Pediatrics*. 2018; 97(1): 131–40.
8. Scheuchenegger A., Lechner E., Wiesinger-Eidenberger G., Weissensteiner M., Wagner O., Schimetta W. et al. Short-term morbidities in moderate and late preterm infants. *Klin. Padiatr*. 2014; 226(4): 216–20. DOI: 10.1055/s-0033-1355394
9. Timofeeva L.A., Kirtbaya A.R., Degtyarev D.N., Sharafutdinova D.R., Tsoi T.A., Karapetyan A.O. i dr. Pozdnie nedonoshennye deti: naskol'ko oni nuzhdayutsya v spetsializirovannoi meditsinskoi pomoshchi? *Neonatologiya: novosti, mneniya, obuchenie*. 2016; 4: 94–101.
10. Timofeeva L.A., Sharafutdinova D.R., Shakaya M.N., Lazareva V.V. Pozdnie nedonoshennye: osnovnye factory riska i iskhody (obzor). 2016; 7(25): 79–83.
11. Visruthan N.K., Agarwal P., Sriram B., Rajadurai V.S. Neonatal outcome of the late preterm infant (34 to 36 weeks): the Singapore story. *Ann. Acad. Med. Singapore*. 2015; 44(7): 235–43.
12. Williams J.E., Pugh Y. The late preterm: a population at risk. *Crit. Care Nurs Clin. North Am*. 2018; 30(4): 431–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.cnc.2018.07.001